

**LIMITING THEOREMS OF PARAMETERS OF ESTIMATES OF
SIMULTANEOUS AUTOREGRESSIVE MODEL**

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Abstract: The nonstationary one-dimensional simultaneous autoregressive model $X_k^n = \alpha(X_{k-1}^n + X_{k+1}^n) + \varepsilon_k, k=1,2,\dots,n-1$ is investigated, where X_0^n and X_n^n are given random variables. We construct new estimates for the parameter α that have more simple limit distributions in the unstable case ($\alpha = \pm 1/2$) in comparison of least square estimates limit distributions of which have complicated form expressing by means of functionals from Wiener process (see, for example in the case $\alpha = 1/2$).

Keywords: Unstable model of simultaneous autoregression; One-dimensional autoregressive model; New estimates; Asymptotical distribution; Functional limit theorem.

I. Introductions

Consider the following simultaneous autoregressive model

$$X_k^n = \begin{cases} \alpha(X_{k-1}^n + X_{k+1}^n) + \varepsilon_k, & k = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1, \\ X_0^n, X_n^n, & \text{given random variables,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where α is unknown parameter, error terms $\{\varepsilon_k, k \in N\}$ are independent identically distributed random variables with $E_{\varepsilon_1} = 0$ and $E_{\varepsilon_1^2} = 1$.

The analysis of simultaneous autoregressive model is of interest in many different fields as geography, geology and agriculture.

Model (1) is called stable, i.e. asymptotically stationary if $|\alpha| < 1/2$ and unstable if $|\alpha| = 1/2$. In case $|\alpha| = \pm 1/2$ the characteristic equation

$$\alpha x^2 - x + \alpha = 0 \text{ has the roots } x = \pm 1.$$

Traditional least square estimate (LSE) for parameter α has complicated structure and in the unstable case has a limit distribution expressing by mean of functionals from Wiener process. For example, in the case of usual AR(1) process, i. e. when

$$X_k = \begin{cases} \alpha X_{k-1}^n + \varepsilon_k, & k = 1, 2, \dots, n \\ 0, & k = 0 \end{cases}$$

The LSE $\hat{\alpha}$ has the following form

$$\hat{\alpha} = \left(\sum_{k=1}^n X_{k-1} \right) / \sum_{k=1}^n X_{k-1}^2$$

and in the unstable case $\alpha = 1$ we have (see, for example, [2])

$$n(\hat{\alpha} - 1) \xrightarrow{w} \frac{1}{2} (w^2(1) - 1) / \int_0^1 w^2(t) dt$$

where $w(t)$, $0 \leq t \leq 1$ is the standard Wiener process.

A.N.Startsev (see: [3]) proposed more simple estimate

$$\alpha_{n,k}^* = (X_k + \dots + X_n) / (X_{k-1} + \dots + X_{n-1})$$

and obtained the following result for $\alpha = 1$

$$P(n\alpha(c)(\alpha_{n,k}^* - 1) < x) \xrightarrow{d} \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\pi} \arctg \left[(x - \rho) / \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \right],$$

where

$$c = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{k}{n} < 1, \quad \alpha(c) = \sqrt{(1-c)(1+2c)/3}, \quad \rho = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{3(1-c)}{1+2c}}.$$

In particular, if $c=1$, then

$$P\left(\sqrt{k(n-k)}(\alpha_{n,k}^* - 1) < x\right) \xrightarrow{d} \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^x \frac{du}{1+u^2}.$$

The LSE $\hat{\alpha}_n$ of the model (1) based on the observation $\{X_k^{(n)}, k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$

has the from

$$\hat{\alpha}_n = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} X_k^{(n)} (X_{k-1}^{(n)} + X_{k+1}^{(n)}) / \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (X_{k-1}^{(n)} + X_{k+1}^{(n)})^2.$$

Baran and Pap (2009) obtained at first the following representation for $X_k^{(n)}$ as a unique solution of the system of linear equation (1) in the case $\alpha = \pm 1/2$

$$X_k^{(n)} = (\pm 1)^k \left(1 - \frac{k}{n}\right) X_0^{(n)} + (\pm 1)^k \frac{k}{n} X_n^{(n)} + 2(1 - k/n) \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} (\pm 1)^{k+l} \varepsilon_1 + 2k/n \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} (\pm 1)^{k+l} (n-l) \varepsilon_1. \quad (2)$$

Then they obtained the following result for $\alpha = 1/2$ assuming for simplicity that $X_0^n = X_n^n = 0$. In what follows we also keep up this assumption.

Theorem A. If $\{\varepsilon_k: k \in \mathbb{N}\}$ are independent identically distributed random variables with $E\varepsilon_1 = 0$, $E\varepsilon_1^2 = 1$ and $E\varepsilon_1^8 < \infty$, then in the case $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$n_2(\hat{\alpha} - \alpha) \xrightarrow{w} \frac{\int_0^1 X_t dw(t)}{2 \int_0^1 (x_t)^2 dt},$$

where

$$x_t = 2(1-t) \int_0^t s dw(s) + 2t \int_t^1 (1-s) dw(s), \quad t \in [0,1].$$

In the present paper are proposed estimates of more simple structure that have more simple limit distribution in unstable case and in the $\alpha = -1/2$ too.

II. Construction of estimates and its asymptotical behavior

It should be noted that estimates in the cases $\alpha = \pm 1/2$ we shall construct by using of different methods.

In the case $\alpha = 1/2$ we obtain a estimation equation by means of summation of the relations (1) along k from 1 to $n - 1$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n X_k^{(n)} = \alpha \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (X_{k-1}^{(n)} + X_{k+1}^{(n)}) + \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \varepsilon_k$$

or in abbreviated form

$$X_n = \alpha Y_n + Z_n.$$

From here we obtain that

$$\alpha_n^* - \alpha = Z_n/Y_n, \tag{3}$$

where $\alpha_n^* = Z_n/Y_n$ is a estimate of parameter α . In the case $\alpha = -1/2$ we construct a estimation equation by means of summation of the relations (1), multiplied at first on $(-1)^k$, along k from 1 to $n-1$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (-1)^{k-1} X_k^{(n)} = \alpha \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (-1)^{k-1} (X_{k-1}^{(n)} + X_{k+1}^{(n)}) + \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (-1)^{k-1} \varepsilon_k$$

or in abbreviated form

$$\widehat{X}_n = \alpha \widehat{Y}_n + \widehat{Z}_n.$$

From here we obtain for the deviation of estimate $\widetilde{\alpha}_n = \widehat{X}_n / \widehat{Y}_n$ from parameter α

$$\widetilde{\alpha}_n - \alpha = \widehat{Z}_n / \widehat{Y}_n \tag{4}$$

For constructed estimates we shall prove the following statement.

Theorem B. Let $\{\varepsilon_k: k \in \mathbb{N}\}$ be independent identically distributed random variables with $E\varepsilon_1 = 0$ and $E\varepsilon_1^2 = 1$.

(i) If $\alpha = 1/2$, then as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$\sigma n^2 (\alpha_n^* - \alpha) \xrightarrow{w} \xi_1 / \xi_2;$$

(ii) If $\alpha = -1/2$, then as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$\sigma n^2 (\widetilde{\alpha}_n - \alpha) \xrightarrow{w} \xi_1 / \xi_2;$$

where $\sigma^2 = 2/15$, (ξ_1, ξ_2) is the normal vector with zero normal mean correlation matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & \sqrt{5/24} \\ \sqrt{5/24} & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Note that in the theorem formulated, the limiting distribution of the estimate α_n^* is much simpler than in Theorem B and, at the same time, the moment constraints on random variables $\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_{n-1}$, are significantly weakened, and the result in the case $\alpha = -1/2$ of the case has no analogues.

Proof of the Theorem B.

We first prove some auxiliary statements about

$$X_n = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} X_k^{(n)} \text{ и } \widetilde{X}_n = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (-1)^k X_k^{(n)}.$$

Lemma 1. In the case $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$

$$X_n = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} k(n-k) \varepsilon_k.$$

Proof of the Lemma 1.

Based on (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{n}{2} X_n &= \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \left[(n-k) \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} l \varepsilon_l + k \sum_{l=k}^{n-1} (n-l) \varepsilon_l \right] = \\ &= \begin{matrix} (n-1) \varepsilon_1 & + & (n-2) \varepsilon_2 & + & (n-3) \varepsilon_3 & + & \dots & + & \varepsilon_{n-1} & + \\ (n-2) \varepsilon_1 & + & 2(n-2) \varepsilon_2 & + & 2(n-3) \varepsilon_3 & + & \dots & + & 2\varepsilon_{n-1} & + \\ (n-3) \varepsilon_1 & + & 2(n-3) \varepsilon_2 & + & 3(n-3) \varepsilon_3 & + & \dots & + & 3\varepsilon_{n-1} & + \\ \dots & & \dots & & \dots & & \dots & & \dots & \\ + & 3\varepsilon_1 & + & 3 \cdot 2\varepsilon_2 & + & 3 \cdot 3\varepsilon_3 & + & \dots & + & (n-3) \varepsilon_{n-1} & + \\ + & 2\varepsilon_1 & + & 2 \cdot 2\varepsilon_2 & + & 2 \cdot 3\varepsilon_3 & + & \dots & + & (n-2) \varepsilon_{n-1} & + \\ + & \varepsilon_1 & + & 2\varepsilon_2 & + & 3\varepsilon_3 & + & \dots & + & (n-1) \varepsilon_{n-1} & . \end{matrix} \end{aligned}$$

From here we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{n}{2} X_n &= (1+2+3+\dots+n-1) \varepsilon_1 + [(n-2) + 2(1+2+\dots+n-2)] \varepsilon_2 + \\ &+ [3(n-3) + 3(1+2+\dots+n-3)] \varepsilon_3 + \dots + (1+2+3+\dots+n-1) \varepsilon_{n-1} = \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} [(1+2+\dots+k-1)(n-k) + k(1+2+\dots+n-k)] \varepsilon_k = \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \left[\frac{(k-1)k(n-k)}{2} + \frac{k(n-k)(n-k+1)}{2} \right] \varepsilon_k = \frac{n}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} k(n-k) \varepsilon_k. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$X_n = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} k(n-k) \varepsilon_k.$$

Lemma 2. When $\alpha = -\frac{1}{2}$

$$\tilde{X}_n = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (-1)^{k-1} k(n-k) \varepsilon_k.$$

Proof of the Lemma 2. From representation (2), by analogy with Lemma 1 we have

$$\frac{n}{2} \tilde{X}_n = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (-1)^{k-1} \left[(n-k) \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} (-1)^{k+l} l \varepsilon_l + k \sum_{l=k}^{n-1} (-1)^{k+l} (n-l) \varepsilon_l \right] =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (n-1)\varepsilon_1 - (n-2)\varepsilon_2 + (n-3)\varepsilon_3 - \dots + (-1)^n \varepsilon_{n-1} + \\
 &+ (n-2)\varepsilon_1 - 2(n-2)\varepsilon_2 + 2(n-3)\varepsilon_3 - \dots + 2(-1)^n \varepsilon_{n-1} + \\
 &+ (n-3)\varepsilon_1 - 2(n-3)\varepsilon_2 + 3(n-3)\varepsilon_3 - \dots + 3(-1)^n \varepsilon_{n-1} + \\
 &\dots \quad \dots \\
 &+ 3\varepsilon_1 - 2 \cdot 3\varepsilon_2 + 3 \cdot 3\varepsilon_3 - \dots + (n-3)(-1)^n \varepsilon_{n-1} + \\
 &+ 2\varepsilon_1 - 2 \cdot 2\varepsilon_2 + 3 \cdot 2\varepsilon_3 - \dots + (n-2)(-1)^n \varepsilon_{n-1} + \\
 &+ \varepsilon_1 - 2 \cdot 1\varepsilon_2 + 3 \cdot 1\varepsilon_3 - \dots + (n-1)(-1)^n \varepsilon_{n-1} .
 \end{aligned}$$

From here we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{n}{2} \tilde{X}_n &= (1+2+3+\dots+n-1)\varepsilon_1 - [(n-2)+2(1+2+\dots+n-2)]\varepsilon_2 + \\
 &+ [3(n-3)+3(1+2+\dots+n-3)]\varepsilon_3 + \dots + (-1)^n (1+2+3+\dots+n-1)\varepsilon_{n-1} = \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (-1)^{k-1} [(1+2+\dots+k-1)(n-k) + k(1+2+\dots+n-k)]\varepsilon_k = \\
 &= \frac{n}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (-1)^{k-1} k(n-k)\varepsilon_k .
 \end{aligned}$$

From this we obtain the assertion of Lemma 2.

Further, in our conditions

$$E(Z_n) = E(\tilde{Z}_n) = E(Y_n) = E(\tilde{Y}_n) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad E(Z_n^2) = E(\tilde{Z}_n^2) = n-1.$$

Now we find the asymptotic behavior $D(Y_n)$ and $D(\tilde{Y}_n)$.

Lemma 3. Under our assumptions, we have for $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$D_n := E(Y_n^2) = E(\tilde{Y}_n^2) \square \sigma^2 n^5,$$

where $\sigma^2 = 2/15$.

Proof of the Lemma 3. From relations (1) we have for $\alpha = \pm 1/2$

$$X_{k-1}^{(n)} + X_{k+1}^{(n)} = \pm 2(X_k^{(n)} - \varepsilon_k)$$

and therefore

$$Y_n = 2 \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (X_k^{(n)} - \varepsilon_k) = 2(X_n - Z_n), \tag{5}$$

$$\tilde{Y}_n = -2 \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (-1)^{k-1} (X_k^{(n)} - \varepsilon_k) = -2(\tilde{X}_n - \tilde{Z}_n). \tag{6}$$

Further, this follows from the lemmas

$$E(X_n^2) = E(\tilde{X}_n^2) = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} k^2 (n-k)^2 \square n^5 \int_0^1 x^2 (1-x)^2 dx = \frac{n^5}{30}$$

and therefore for

$$n \rightarrow \infty$$

$$E(Y_n^2) \square 4E(X_n^2), \quad E(\tilde{Y}_n^2) \square 4E(\tilde{X}_n^2).$$

This ends the proof.

Returning to the proof of Theorem A, from (3) and (4), taking into account (5) and (6), we have

$$\alpha_n^* - \alpha = \frac{Z_n}{2(X_n - Z_n)}, \quad \tilde{\alpha}_n - \alpha = -\frac{\tilde{Z}_n}{2(\tilde{X}_n - \tilde{Z}_n)}. \quad (7)$$

If, $X_n^* = D_n^{-1}X_n$, $Y_n^* = D_n^{-1}Y_n$, $Z_n^* = Z_n/E(Z_n^2)$, $\tilde{Z}_n^* = \tilde{Z}_n/E(\tilde{Z}_n^2)$, then relations (7), we can rewrite in the following form

$$2\sigma n^2(\alpha_n^* - \alpha) = \frac{Z_n^*}{X_n^* + o_p(1)}, \quad 2\sigma n^2(\tilde{\alpha}_n - \alpha) = -\frac{\tilde{Z}_n^*}{\tilde{X}_n^* + o_p(1)}, \quad (8)$$

Where $o_p(1) \xrightarrow{P} 0$, at $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Now let us prove that the random vectors (Z_n^*, X_n^*) and $(\tilde{Z}_n^*, \tilde{X}_n^*)$ are asymptotically normal. For this, it is sufficient to prove that (based on the Cramer – Wald method) one-dimensional random variables $S_n = t_1 Z_n^* + t_2 X_n^*$ and $\tilde{S}_n = t_1 \tilde{Z}_n^* + t_2 \tilde{X}_n^*$ are asymptotically normal. The quantities S_n and $\tilde{S}_n$ are represented in the form

$$S_n = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} a_{n,k} \varepsilon_k, \quad \tilde{S}_n = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (-1)^{k-1} a_{n,k} \varepsilon_k,$$

where $a_{n,k} = \frac{t_1}{\sqrt{n-1}} + \frac{k(n-k)}{D_n} t_2.$

Using Lemma 3, from this we have

$$B_n^2 := E(S_n^2) = E(\tilde{S}_n^2) = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \left(\frac{t_1}{\sqrt{n-1}} + \frac{k(n-k)}{D_n} t_2 \right)^2 =$$

$$= t_1^2 + \frac{2t_1 t_2}{\sqrt{n-1} D_n} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} k(n-k) + \frac{t_2^2}{D_n^2} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} k^2 (n-k)^2 \square t_1^2 + 2\rho t_1 t_2 + t_2^2,$$

where $\rho = \sqrt{5/24}$.

Now you need to check the Lindeberg condition for S_n and $\tilde{S}_n$:

$$L_n := \frac{1}{B_n^2} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \int_{|x| > \frac{\varepsilon B_n}{|a_{n,k}|}} a_{n,k}^2 x^2 dF_{\varepsilon_k}(x) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{при } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Really

$$L_n = \frac{1}{B_n^2} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} a_{n,k}^2 \int_{|x| > \frac{\varepsilon B_n}{|a_{n,k}|}} x^2 dF_{\varepsilon_1}(x) \rightarrow 0,$$

because

$$|a_{n,k}| = \frac{k(n-k)}{D_n} |t_1| + \frac{1}{\sqrt{n-1}} |t_2| \leq \frac{n}{4D_n} |t_1| + \frac{1}{\sqrt{n-1}} |t_2| \square \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \left(\frac{1}{4\sigma} |t_1| + |t_2| \right) \rightarrow 0.$$

So we have

$$E \exp \left\{ it_1 Z_n^* + it_2 X_n^* \right\} = E \exp \{ iS_n \} \rightarrow \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} (t_1^2 + 2\rho t_1 t_2 + t_2^2) \right\},$$

where $\rho = \sqrt{5/24}$.

Remark: It is known that the distribution function $F(x)$ of random variables

ξ_1/ξ_2 has the following form

$$F(x) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\pi} \operatorname{arctg} \frac{x - \rho}{\sqrt{1 - \rho^2}}, \quad -\infty < x < \infty.$$

For the one-dimensional simultaneous autoregression model

$$X_k^{(n)} = \alpha \left(X_{k-1}^{(n)} + X_{k+1}^{(n)} \right) + \varepsilon_k \quad \text{with the given } X_0^{(n)} = X_n^{(n)} = 0 \quad \text{new estimates for the}$$

parameter are constructed α and their limiting distributions are found in critical cases $\alpha = \pm 1/2$.

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